

Immortality and Resurrection of the Dead

Probable Timeline

Timeline for achieving immortality, (most probably) by merging people with AI and thus becoming hybrid.

2030s': Immortality (for the First Human)

2040s': Immortality (for the Very Rich)

2050s': For the Rich

2060s': For the Middle Class

2070s': For the Poor

2080s': For the Very Poor

Within half a century, from the 2030's till 2080's, Immortality will become available from the very rich to the very poor.

Timeline for the resurrection of the dead through science, using Biotech and DNA.

21st Century: Resurrection achieved in flies or mosquitoes. (First Step).

22nd Century: Resurrection in mice.

23rd Century: Resurrection in cats or dogs.

24th -25th Century: Resurrection (hopefully) in humans. (Last Step).

10th Millenium-50th Millennium: All the rest of humanity (100-106 billion people resurrected).

By then, humanity will have terraformed the entire Solar System (which can potentially hold 50 trillion people) and part of the Milky Way galaxy (which can hold far more than that).

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01/25/2024